

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PHAM****FIRST NAME: ANH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (Windows 11)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. The structure of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-11)
3. Some rules of thumb (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
4. When not to cite (EUCLID 2021, 37)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC WRITING COURSEPACK RP1

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing can be challenging unless one pursues it as a profession or has a passion. Academic publishing requires a high effort and can often be daunting, even for doctoral-level practitioners. Nevertheless, with adequate instruction and conquering the first mindset of reluctance, everybody has the potential to become a proficient writer. I am fascinated by the notion of "academic writing" and the distinction between scientific writing and other methodologies, as exemplified in Euclid's preliminary investigation of writing styles. As a collaborative journalist with a background in multiple business writing courses, I recognize the importance of adhering to various academic writing styles. Doing so showcases professionalism and expertise, promotes a focused writing approach, upholds copyright principles, and cultivates self-discipline.

I have reviewed the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1) using Turabian style, written and revised by Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021). Turabian is a specialized version of the Chicago style that was specifically developed for academics and students. The textbook provides a comprehensive training curriculum that prepares students for their upcoming journey and enhances their English language proficiency. I am confident that

EUCLID's technique will ensure that learners, including myself, get a comprehensive understanding of academic writing style choices and different principles of language communication between British English and American English.

In my response paper one (RP1), I examine five (05) important facets and have more interest in point number five, which relates to the matter of plagiarism in scholarly writing, and present my arguments alongside number four – When not to cite. While Grammarly's word similarity checker may be acceptable for essays, it may not have the same accuracy as Turnitin in identifying plagiarism, particularly for meeting the dissertation standards. Hence, I highly recommend that the institution provide students with access to Turnitin, if possible, for the purpose of producing dissertations or scientific papers intended for publication.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Students at Euclid University are introduced to academic writing in the first study guide. This fourth version of the period one coursepack offers guidelines for international academic and professional paper writing, much like the introduction page of the textbook (EUCLID 2021, 2). Academic essays are factual written works produced as a component of academic research (EUCLID 2021, 7).

References are the exclusive means of defense against plagiarism, which is a significant violation in academic textbooks (EUCLID 2021, 5). Distinguishing academic writing from regular writing can be done by examining the presence of specific citation rules. References must be provided in all academic essays. Regardless of the stylistic variations between Chicago and Harvard styles, academic writing consistently adheres to established guidelines for citing sources. This includes the use of in-text citations as well as footnotes or references for additional notes when required.

In addition to carefully considering the perspectives being debated (EUCLID 2021, 14), academic writing requires meticulousness and is based on scientific data. Nevertheless, academic writing can employ creativity to engage readers without producing unverifiable information. Prior to everything else, to prevent perplexing the reader, academic writing must adhere to grammatical accuracy, while satisfying the writing style prerequisites and criteria of scientific journals.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF THE ESSAY

By standard, an essay is structured in the following manner: it begins with an introduction that presents the topic and statement; followed by a body that contains a comprehensive analysis and supporting evidence; and concludes with a summary of the main points. However, what is different, and intriguing is the way in which an essay is written is concretized by bullet points in the essay writing guide in the coursepack edited and edited in 2021 (EUCLID 2021, 10).

For example, the introduction transitions from a broad overview to more specific details in the Introduction section: At the beginning, we provide a brief introduction by presenting the topic area(s) with a generic and broad opening phrase or two. Then, we answer the question with a clear and concise thesis statement. Finally, we end by summarizing the main points or providing a 'road map' of the essay.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB

I concur that it is entirely acceptable to express a statement such as: "I will argue that" (EUCLID 2021, 12). Daly (1996, 2), a well-known ecological economist, also states that "important concepts are more dialectical than analytic."¹ The genuine and professional academic community thrives on engaging in debates and valuing differences, as this fosters the continuous improvement of new thoughts and theories for the betterment of humanity.

In EUCLID (2021, 13), Cleenewerck & Gulma emphasize the importance of avoiding dull and awkward writing. I concur with this directive. However, the process of creating written content for research and scientific publications differs from the act of writing fictional stories. Scientific writing exhibits clarity and focus is grounded on evidence, and is protected by copyright laws. It is essential to uphold and treat academic discipline and values with dignity.

5) WHEN NOT TO CITE

We do not need to cite the source of material if it is common knowledge that may be accessed in many different places (EUCLID 2021, 37). The authors also hold that if an idea is repeated in many sources at our disposal, we can generally infer that it is common knowledge. Nonetheless, it is necessary to reference commonly accepted information when a researcher seeks to consolidate viewpoints that support a specific thesis. Therefore, quoting the so-called "common knowledge" is appropriate in this scenario. However, engaging in excessive citation is not recommended as it indicates a lack of comprehension of the research subject.

From my perspective, citations generally encompass five (05) scenarios:

- (1) Quoting distinctive perspectives relevant to the research topic;
- (2) Referencing novel viewpoints within the field of study;

¹ "Important concepts are more dialectical than analytic, in the sense that they have evolving penumbras with partially overlap with their "other." Analytic concepts have no overlap with their other, so the law of contradictions holds – that is, B cannot be both A and non A. But for dialectical concepts there are cases in which makes sense to say that B is both A and non-A.

- (3) Citing ideas findings from like-minded individuals to garner support or to confirm an important claim;
- (4) Quoting contrasting perspectives to fosters constructive debates; and
- (5) When in doubt, cite.

6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is the act of not giving credit to the original source of information that a writer has utilized (EUCLID 2021, 34). There are two types of plagiarism, and both are wrong (EUCLID 2021, 14). First, plagiarism is using someone else's words without quotation marks. When using sources' words, use quotation marks, not footnotes. Instead of copying a source, repeat the topic in our words or use quotation marks. Second, plagiarism occurs when we use ideas without citing them. Plagiarism is a serious academic misconduct, and one may face hard discipline. The recent plagiarism scandal involving Harvard President Claudine Gay is a prominent illustration of plagiarism, even among those holding esteemed positions in leading colleges globally. Plagiarism by accident and carelessness can be tolerated, but plagiarism due to self-interested motives in academia is unacceptable, even as the recipient of the prestigious Nobel Prize.

To prevent allegations of plagiarism, students must include ample citations from credible sources. Paraphrasing is an effective method for expressing a writer's perspective, but it is crucial to provide accurate citations. However, we must choose a distinct writing style to convey our views, one that differs from the style employed by the author (EUCLID 2021, 36). Optimally, one should employ their own vocabulary, while simultaneously employing professional software to verify plagiarism, in order to safeguard the writer's integrity.

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA 401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1) is an excellent textbook, but I prefer to call it an academic writing bible. For me, it is worthwhile to preserve and look up not only during the study period, but also for future activities such as producing scientific publications, teaching, and research. Although students can present 5 to 7 concepts in their Response papers, the handbook's learning value extends well beyond that.

I particularly enjoyed Chapter Seven: Latin Abbreviations and Expressions. I used to be perplexed when I encountered these abbreviations and expressions, but that is no longer the case. I appreciate the opportunity to possess this invaluable guide on academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Daly, Herman E. 1996. *Beyond Growth: The Economics of Sustainable Development*. Boston: Beacon Press.

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